

DETERMINATION OF OPTIMAL PLACEMENT OF SPACER DAMPERS ON OVERHEAD HIGH-VOLTAGE TRANSMISSION LINES USING THE FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

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ABSTRACT

This report concentrates on the optimal placement of spacer dampers. A literature survey is conducted on the oscillation of bundle conductors, and the mathematical model is developed. A span length is modelled using the finite element program – ADINA. The spacer dampers were varied in different positions hence, the damping factor is calculated for each and every position in order to find the positions with high damping factor. Recommendation for placement of spacer dampers is given based on the analysis of the result obtained from the ADINA program.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of multi-conductor bundles to transport economically large amounts of energy has been established for several decades [1]. Conductor spacers rapidly became important pieces of hardware aimed at maintaining the geometry of bundles to meet the requirement of electrical performance. However their role soon evolved as more important component to keep required distance on bundled conductors and to dissipate energy absorbed by bundled conductors from environmental conditions.

2. CONDUCTOR MOTION

2.1 Aeolian vibration

When a laminar stream of air passes across a cylinder shape, such as conductor or an overhead earth wire, the formation of alternating vortices (eddies) behind them creates alternating pressures which tend to produce movement at right angles to the direction of the air flow. The frequency range is typically between 3 and 150 Hz and the amplitude could vary between 0.01 to 1 conductor diameter [1, 2].

2.2 Wake-induced vibration

This type of vibration is confined to bundle conductors. It is an aerodynamic instability problem arising from one conductor lying in the wake of an upstream conductor. The leeward conductors that lie in the wakes of windward conductors are subjected to forces not

experienced by single conductors. The frequency range is typically between 0.15 and 10 Hz and the amplitude could vary between 0.5 and 80 conductor diameters [3].

2.3 Galloping

Conductor galloping is a very low frequency-high amplitude, primarily vertical motion of the conductor. Moderately strong, steady crosswinds acting upon an asymmetrically iced conductor surface usually cause it. Even a very thin ice (1 mm to 2mm) has been known to cause galloping. The frequency range is typically between 0.08 and 3 Hz [3].

3. PRINCIPLES OF MODELLING

Figure 3.1 Physical model of four bundle conductor

The mathematical model is formulated by using the Hamilton's principle as given below:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} (\delta T - \delta V + \overline{\delta W_{nc}}) dt = 0, \delta q_k = 0, k = 1, 2, \dots, n; t = t_1, t_2 \dots \dots \dots (3.1)$$

Where (δV) - potential energy, (δT) - kinetic energy and ($\overline{\delta W_{nc}(t)}$) - virtual work, and where $\overline{\delta W_{nc}} = 0$ for conservative systems [4]. But in this case, the extended Hamilton's principle will be expressed as:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} (\delta T - \delta V + \overline{\delta W_{nc}}) dt = 0, \delta y(x, t) = 0, 0 \leq x \leq L, t = t_1, t_2 \dots \dots \dots (3.2)$$

The kinetic energy including transverse motion and torsion is given by:

$$T(t) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \rho(x) \left[\frac{\partial y(x, t)}{\partial t} \right]^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \rho(x) \left[\frac{\partial z(x, t)}{\partial t} \right]^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} \sum m_i \left[\left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right] \dots \dots (3.3)$$

Where the term $\frac{1}{2} \sum m_i \left[\left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right]$ represents the kinetic energy of the spacer damper at point i –represented by \mathbf{B} on figure 3.1 above. m_i is mass of spacer damper. The virtual work of the non-conservative distributed force is

$$\overline{\delta W}_{nc}(t) = \int_0^L f(x,t) [\delta y(x,t) + \delta z(x,t)] dx \dots\dots\dots (3.4)$$

The potential energy requires some elaboration: it is observed that the potential energy arises from the tension restoring the cable to its equilibrium position and also torsion. Figure (3.2) clearly illustrates the changes in y and z of the cable when exposed to torsion.

Figure 3.2: Differential element dx in displaced position

Figure 3.3: Dimensional change of cable under torsion and transverse motion

The tensile force T must work through the difference in length $ds' - dx$ to restore equilibrium.

$$V(t) = \int_0^L T(x) [ds'(x,t) - dx] \dots\dots\dots (3.5)$$

From figure (3.3), the value of ds' can be obtained as follows:

$$ds' = \left[1 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right]^{0.5} dx \cong \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right] dx \dots\dots\dots (3.6)$$

From figure (3.3), it can be seen that $dz = \phi ds'$ so that it can also be denoted by this relationship. The potential energy after inserting equation (3.6) into equation (3.5) will yield:

$$V(t) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L T(x) \left[\left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right] dx \dots\dots\dots (3.7)$$

Note that the partial differentiation of y and z can be denoted by θ and ϕ respectively. The variation in the kinetic energy is given by:

$$\delta T = \int_0^L \rho \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \delta y dx + \int_0^L \rho \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \delta z dx + \sum m_i \left[\frac{\partial y}{\partial t} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \delta y + \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \delta z \right]_i$$

Integration by parts with respect to time will yield

$$= - \left[\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left(\int_0^L \rho \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2} \delta y dx + \int_0^L \rho \frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial t^2} \delta z dx \right) dt + \sum m_i \left[\left(\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2} \delta y \right) + \left(\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial t^2} \delta z \right) \right] dt \right] \dots (3.8)$$

Where $\delta y = \delta z = 0$ at $t = t_1$ and $t = t_2$, for the spacer damper alone the translations can either be along the z-axis or the y-axis or both at the same time. The right hand side top corner of the spacer damper is enlarged to indicate the damping (**C**) and the stiffness (**K**) coefficients for the spacer damper (see figure 3.1 above). These quantities will be included in the finite element implementation. For the spacer damper, translations z and y are dependent on each other through the constraint equation, $L^2 = z^2 + y^2$. Therefore the velocity of m_i , $v_i = \sqrt{\dot{y}^2 + \dot{z}^2}$. Assuming that the angular velocity $\omega = \dot{\theta}$ is uniform, then

velocity $\left| \dot{y} \right| = |\omega y|$. The variation in the potential energy can be similarly written as:

$$\delta V = \int_0^L T \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\delta y) dx + \int_0^L T \frac{\partial z}{\partial x} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\delta z) dx \dots (3.9)$$

Performing integration by parts, we obtain

$$\delta V = \left[T \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \delta y \right]_{x=L} - \left[T \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \delta y \right]_{x=0} - \int_0^L \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(T \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right) \delta y dx + \left[T \frac{\partial z}{\partial x} \delta z \right]_{x=L} - \left[T \frac{\partial z}{\partial x} \delta z \right]_{x=0} - \int_0^L \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(T \frac{\partial z}{\partial x} \right) \delta z dx \dots (3.10)$$

We will first assume that the cable vibrates along the y-axis for simplicity and $\dot{y} \approx \omega y$ therefore $\dot{y}^2 \approx \omega^2 y^2$. Inserting the equations of the variations of the potential energy (δV), kinetic energy ($\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta T dt$) and virtual work ($\delta W_{nc}(t)$) into the Hamilton's equation gives,

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left\{ \int_0^L \left[-\rho \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(T \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right) + f \right] \delta y dx - \left[T \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \delta y + \sum m_i \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2} \delta y \right]_{x=L} + \left[T \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \delta y \right]_{x=0} \right\} dt \dots (3.11)$$

At this point, we invoke the arbitrariness of the virtual displacement δy . We first set $\delta y = 0$ at $x = 0$ and $x = L$ and assign values of $\delta y(x, t)$ over the interval $0 < x < L$. Under these circumstances equation (3.11) can be satisfied only if the coefficient of $\delta y(x, t)$ is zero over the same interval. Hence, we set

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(T \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right) + f = \rho \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2}, 0 < x < L \dots (3.12)$$

Then with the integral in Equation (3.12) disposed of, we once again invoke the arbitrariness of the virtual displacement and state that δy is chosen such that $T \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \delta y = 0, \quad x = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad x = L$ and $\left(\left(T \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right) + m_i \omega_i^2 y_i \right) \delta y = 0, \quad x = L_i \dots \dots \dots (3.14)$

where L_i represents the location points of the spacer dampers. The term $m_i \omega_i^2 y_i$ represents the inertia force exerted by the spacer dampers on the conductor due to translation in the y-direction. Equation (3.14) can be satisfied in two ways, namely, by setting either $\left(T \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right) = 0$ or $\delta y = 0$ at $x = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad x = L$. The first is recognised as the vertical force, which cannot be zero for all times at a fixed end. On the other hand, the displacement is zero at the fixed end, so that Equation (3.14) is satisfied by setting:

$y(0, t) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad y(L, t) = 0$. Similarly, Equation (3.14) is satisfied if either

$\left(\left(T \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right) + m_i \omega_i^2 y_i \right) \delta y \Big|_{x=L_i}$ or δy is zero at $x = L_i$. But the displacement cannot be zero for all times at $x = L_i$. Hence, Equation (3.14) is satisfied by setting

$$T \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right)_i + m_i \omega_i^2 y_i = 0. \quad x = L_i \dots \dots \dots (3.15)$$

This is the derivation of the boundary value problem, which consists of the differential equation. Hence the stiffness and the damping factor can be included in the above equation as indicated in figure 3.3 (b). Therefore Equation 3.15 becomes:

$$T \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right)_i + m_i \omega_i^2 y_i + k y_i + C y_i = 0. \quad x = L_i$$

Hence we need to find the y-displacement of the string at any later time. We assume the following:

1. The mass of the string per unit length is constant.
2. The string is perfectly elastic and does not offer any resistance to bending.
3. The tension of the string is so large that the gravitational force on the string can be neglected and the distributed force f is zero.

Equation (3.12) reduces to, $\left(\frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2} \right) = a^2 \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x^2}, \quad 0 < x < L$ where $a^2 = \frac{T}{\rho}$, and a is a constant. The displacement of the string at any later time may be given by the following Fourier equation:

$$y(x, t) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{L} \int_0^{L_i} f(x) \sin \frac{m\pi x}{L} dx \right) \sin \frac{m\pi x}{L} \cos \frac{m\pi a t}{L} \quad 0 < x < L, \quad x \neq L_i \dots (3.16)$$

where $f(x)$ is the initial shape of the string and m is the normal modes of vibration of the string. The initial shape of the conductor at time $t=0$ may be approximated by $y = x^2/2C$ as a parabola representing the span sag.

The equations described here are implemented in a finite element programme. Similar formulations were implemented in the ADINA program, including effects of the viscous damping model. (See the following section) We can approximate the y-displacement of the cable at the location of the spacer dampers. Hence the log decrement and damping factor can then be calculated.

4. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

4.1 Modelling of bundle conductor

The finite element program (ADINA) was used to model a quad bundle conductor. The figure below shows a typical quad bundle conductor.

Figure 4.1: Node 41 at point 21 zoomed in

4.2 Geometry

Table 4.1: Quad Bundle conductor's configuration

Span length	400 m
Conductor diameter	26,9 mm
Conductor Separation	450 mm

4.3 Material Properties

Table 4.2: Material properties

Mass per unit length	1.34 Kg/m
Young's Modulus	7×10^{10}
Poisson's ratio	0.33
Density	2710 Kg/m^3
Material	Aluminum

4.4 Boundary Conditions

Table 4.3: Boundary conditions

Fixity	Fixed at both ends
Tension	23604.4 N
Initial Strain	0.00059385
Degrees of freedom	X, Y, Z –Translation and Rotation
Time Simulated	1000 seconds

Each of the four, 400-m conductors has 41 points and subdivided into 80 elements and 81 nodes. The element group 1 (truss or cable) is used to model the conductor. The distance apart from each point is 10 m and the spacer dampers are placed at the points indicated. Each conductor is divided as follows.

Figure 4.2: Points corresponding to nodes on a conductor

4.5 Quad Spacer Dampers

Table 4.4: Material Properties

Young's Modulus	7×10^{10}
Poisson's ratio	0.33
Density	2710 Kg/m ³
Material	Aluminum

Here the spacer dampers are modelled using element group 2 (Isobeam), with a rectangle cross-section of 0.05 X 0.02 m² and material properties are those of aluminium. The rotation at the junction between a spacer damper and conductors is restricted, corresponding to a rigidly clamped joint.

5. RESULTS

After running the program, the displacement versus time graphs were plotted for each node on the ADINA program. A typical response graph for node 41 is shown in the figure below.

Figure 5.1: Typical Response graph for node 41

The above figure clearly shows that there is an oscillation with decaying amplitude. A convenient measure of the amount of damping in a single-degree-of-freedom system is the drop in amplitude at the completion of one cycle of vibration.

Least squares approach method is used to calculate the logarithmic decrement and viscous damping factor for each and every nodal point. The following equations are used [4].

$$\left(\sum_{j=1}^n y_j^2 \right) a + \left(\sum_{j=1}^n y_j \right) b = \sum_{j=1}^n (\ln x_j) y_j ; \quad \left(\sum_{j=1}^n y_j \right) a + nb = \sum_{j=1}^n (\ln x_j) \quad (5.1, 5.2)$$

Where: $j = 1, 2, \dots, 50$, $y_j = j - 1$, and $\delta = -a$. Inserting the values of the pick amplitude obtained from the graph and solving for a and b using the spread sheet, the values of a and b are obtained, and it follows that: $\delta = -a = 0.053204$ and, $\zeta = \delta / \sqrt{(2\pi)^2 + \delta^2} = 0.008464$.

6. ANALYSIS OF A QUAD BUNDLE CONDUCTOR WITH 9 SPACER DAMPERS

The logarithmic decrement and viscous damping factor above are calculated only for node 41 on a quad bundle conductor with nine spacer dampers using Microsoft Excel. The same procedure was followed in order to calculate logarithmic decrement and viscous damping factor of all the nodes that are monitored. The simulation is started from a quad bundle conductor; 400m span length with a single spacer damper to the one with nine spacer dampers. The simulation is carried over for the second round. One spacer damper is shifted ten meters to the right and then to the left from its initial position, leaving the other spacer dampers fixed in their respective positions. The simulation is carried over for the two new positions of that particular spacer damper and the corresponding values of logarithmic decrement and viscous damping factor are obtained. The same procedure is applied to the rest of the spacer dampers for the whole span length. The objective of the variation of the spacer dampers positions is to obtain the trend, whether to shift spacer dampers to the right or left

The following tables show the values of logarithmic decrement and viscous damping factor after the spacer dampers were shifted to specified positions.

Table 6.1: Variation of positions (nine spacer dampers), Set of δ and ξ at selected nodal positions

Node Number	Shifted damper from	Point 21 to 20	Point 21 to 22	Point 11 to 12	Point 11 to 10	Point 31 to 30	Point 31 to 32	Point 8 to 7	Point 8 to 9	Point 34 to 33	Point 34 to 35
11	δ	0.05315	0.051256	0.05311	0.05273	0.051217	0.051176	0.05245	0.05383	0.05281	0.050933
	ξ	0.008345	0.008157	0.008452	0.008392	0.008151	0.008145	0.008347	0.008567	0.008405	0.008106
15	δ	0.05132	0.052436	0.05294	0.05261	0.043783	0.05324	0.05232	0.05285	0.05235	0.051054
	ξ	0.008168	0.008345	0.008425	0.008373	0.008969	0.008473	0.008327	0.008411	0.008332	0.008125
21	δ	0.050165	0.051514	0.05296	0.05268	0.051443	0.051398	0.05242	0.05297	0.05244	0.05026
	ξ	0.007984	0.008199	0.008429	0.008384	0.008187	0.00818	0.008343	0.008430	0.008346	0.008799
31	δ	0.053399	0.053404	0.05400	0.05338	0.052346	0.052273	0.05307	0.05368	0.05310	0.05214
	ξ	0.008498	0.008499	0.008594	0.008495	0.008331	0.008319	0.008446	0.008543	0.008451	0.008299
41	δ	0.052975	0.052821	0.05492	0.05542	0.052829	0.052686	0.05351	0.05417	0.05359	0.053367
	ξ	0.008843	0.008406	0.008741	0.008820	0.008408	0.008385	0.008516	0.008621	0.008529	0.008493
51	δ	0.052739	0.052593	0.05399	0.05319	0.052516	0.052452	0.05322	0.05397	0.05218	0.051549
	ξ	0.008393	0.00837	0.008593	0.008465	0.008358	0.008348	0.008470	0.008589	0.008304	0.008204
61	δ	0.052369	0.052269	0.05351	0.05323	0.052716	0.052416	0.05074	0.05350	0.05293	0.05216
	ξ	0.008335	0.008319	0.008516	0.008472	0.008397	0.008342	0.008075	0.008515	0.008424	0.008301
67	δ	0.052413	0.05230	0.05324	0.05296	0.054582	0.052503	0.05267	0.05324	0.05266	0.053656
	ξ	0.008342	0.008325	0.008473	0.008429	0.008687	0.008356	0.008382	0.008473	0.008381	0.008539
71	δ	0.051911	0.053786	0.05309	0.05285	0.052228	0.053532 42	0.05261	0.05334	0.05262	0.05165
	ξ	0.008262	0.00856	0.008499	0.008411	0.00812	0.008473	0.008373	0.008489	0.008374	0.00811

Figure 6.1: Trends of shifting spacer dampers

Node Number	Shifted damper from	Point 26 to 27	Point 26 to 25	Point 36 to 35	Point 36 to 37	Point 16 to 17	Point 16 to 15	Point 6 to 7	Point 6 to 5
11	8	0.051064	0.05277	0.05311	0.05273	0.05313	0.05303	0.05383	0.05281
15	5	0.008127	0.008398	0.008452	0.008392	0.008456	0.008440	0.008568	0.008405
21	8	0.052238	0.05265	0.05294	0.05261	0.05232	0.05307	0.05285	0.05235
31	5	0.008314	0.00838	0.008426	0.008374	0.008327	0.008445	0.08411	0.008331
41	8	0.053332	0.05276	0.05296	0.05268	0.05242	0.05293	0.05297	0.05244
51	5	0.008488	0.008396	0.008428	0.008383	0.008342	0.008424	0.008430	0.008345
61	8	0.057528	0.05340	0.05400	0.05338	0.05342	0.05376	0.05368	0.05310
67	5	0.009156	0.008498	0.008562	0.008495	0.008501	0.008556	0.008543	0.008451
71	8	0.053585	0.05453	0.05492	0.05542	0.05349	0.05415	0.05417	0.05359
11	5	0.008528	0.008678	0.008741	0.008820	0.008513	0.008617	0.008622	0.008529
15	8	0.05243	0.05367	0.05399	0.05319	0.05331	0.05394	0.05397	0.05218
21	5	0.008345	0.008541	0.008593	0.008465	0.008484	0.008584	0.008589	0.008305
31	8	0.05342	0.05334	0.05351	0.05323	0.05292	0.05347	0.05350	0.05293
41	5	0.00835	0.008490	0.008516	0.008471	0.008422	0.008509	0.008575	0.008424
51	8	0.0523	0.05300	0.05324	0.05296	0.05264	0.05320	0.05324	0.05266
61	5	0.008365	0.008433	0.008474	0.008429	0.008378	0.008467	0.008474	0.008381
71	8	0.05	0.05294	0.05309	0.05285	0.05264	0.05311	0.05334	0.05262
11	5	0.008400	0.008425	0.008449	0.008411	0.008378	0.008453	0.08490	0.008378

7. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Figure 6.1, shows the trends of shifting spacer dampers. The results show that the spacer dampers must be more concentrated towards the centre, for efficient damping. The spacer dampers are placed to the positions having the higher damping factor and the recommended placement for a 400m bundle conductor is as follow:

Tower	40 m	40 m	30 m	40 m	60 m	30 m	50 m	30 m	40 m	40 m	Tower
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This spacing scheme has yet to be tested at ESKOM's Kroonstad test station.

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